

Moe Mathews - Investor, Developer, Builder and Wholesaler

Moe Mathews is [an investor, developer, builder and wholesaler](#). As a real estate professional, who has been in business for many years, Moe enjoys working with buyers and sellers that are mostly referrals from his satisfied customers.

Moe has helped clients buy and sell everything from condos to luxury homes, always with outstanding customer service. As a passionate professional, he strives to help his clients save money and accomplish their goals.

The personal attention Moe Mathews provides to his clients is at the forefront of everything he does, whether it's buying, selling, relocating, or investing.

Skills and Certifications

While excellent communication and negotiation skills are important when working with buyers, Moe's ability to match buyers with the perfect home is by far his greatest strength. Moreover, he assists his buyers in the security, maintenance, and rental marketing of their homes well beyond the close of escrow.

[Moe Mathews](#) is proud to be affiliated with the book “Elite Real Estate Professionals, Top Leaders In The Industry!”. This book reached number 1 on the Amazon Best Seller List, on the day the book debuted. He wrote a chapter that was a vital and valuable contribution to the success of the book.

His qualifications include the Short Sales and Foreclosure Resource Certification (SFR) and the Certified Distressed Property Expert designation (CDPE). He also serves as an investor wealth coach.

While raising their two children, both graduates of Virginia Commonwealth University, Moe has combined his business life with raising his family.

Education

Following his graduation from Douglas Freeman High School, Moe Mathews [attended the University of Maryland](#). In addition to obtaining a Bachelor's Degree in Computer Science from the University of Maryland, he obtained a Minor in Computer Studies in addition to a Major in Business Administration.

In order to help his clients achieve their real estate goals, Moe Mathews brings unmatched insight into local real estate trends. Over the past two decades, he has successfully sold homes, so you can be assured he understands how to help you find the perfect home for you.

Moe is dedicated to helping his clients achieve their real estate goals by providing an unparalleled level of personal service.